

IT infrastructure requirements based on a data protection by design and default approach

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1. Definitions

The documents are built on the [1+MG Glossary](#). In particular, the following expressions are used:

- **Metadata:** a set of data that describes and gives information about other data. Metadata do not include any data that are processed to produce any results of the data use such as health or genetic data. Metadata can be personal data where they contain information on the subject level (e.g. consent decisions of an individual data subject)
- **Data collections:** Data collections are data that come from the same collection context from the same controller(s) and can be characterised with non-personal metadata. A data collection can e.g. refer to data of a cohort or a public registry.
- **Records:** Data related to individual data subjects
- **Data set:** Data that are grouped in a certain context, e.g. for a user's access.
- **Enriched data:** data where additional information is added, e.g. annotations
- **Derived data:** data that have been created by alteration of the original data (e.g. through data curation)

2. Background: 1+MG initiative

The 1+MG initiative originates from a joint [Declaration](#) signed by the governments of 13 countries on Digital Day in 2018. Since then 11 more countries have signed to this declaration. The aim of 1+MG is to enable secure access to genomics and the corresponding clinical data across Europe for better research, personalised healthcare and health policy making. A pan-European genomic cohort and a corresponding governance model is to be established in order to achieve better health for citizens, future sustainability of health systems, and to boost large-scale data-driven biomedical and clinical R&D in Europe.

To realise the goals, the countries support the development of technical specifications for secure access and cross-border exchange, secure infrastructure and tools to enable cross-border sharing or analysis of genetic and other data-sets and promote the use of open standards and data management systems to ensure interoperability of genomic and other health data with a view to enhance research on personalised medicine and genetic diseases.

3. Data life cycle in 1+MG

The following assumption on the data life cycle in 1+MG was made.

The data journey

The following stages are considered for the data journey.

1. Data preparation: Pre-processing to agreed standards, annotation with metadata etc.
2. Data inclusion: Physical transfer of data incl., legal transfer of data to 1+MG to enable visibility in data catalogue
3. Data storage and management: Including GDPR compliant processing environment, data versioning etc.
4. Data discovery: Discovery of data using GDPR compliant application programming interfaces (APIs)
5. Data access: A mechanism(s) by which the party acting as the controller for data access/disclosure can authorise access to select dataset(s)
6. Data use: Data processing for the approved purposes to obtain a result
7. Data archiving for the approved purposes (where necessary for a respective purpose)

Data's life in 1+MG

Data included in 1+MG have already been generated in a different context (primary use) and are subsequently brought into 1+MG by the Data Provider. It is the responsibility of the Data Provider that the data are characterised with relevant metadata and curated into a data model accepted by 1+MG. 1+MG and potentially national / local structures will support Data Providers. Data are uploaded by a Data Provider, alongside with the associated metadata. The data are ingested into the system and relevant metadata made available in the data catalogue. A user may choose from the data catalogue relevant data collections or, after registration for research use, even individual records across different collections and countries. Based on the selection, the user launches an access request. The signing official of the user's institution must confirm this request unless the user is whitelisted in the system, which flags that the researcher has a permanently confirmed right in the home institutions to apply for access. The information on the request with all relevant information is sent to the 1+MG central office of the central 1+MG Data Access Committee (central DAC) and the relevant National Coordination Points. The central office communicates to the relevant National Coordination Points the justified access decision of the central DAC. In case of research access, the National Coordination Point (after consultation of relevant stakeholders, where applicable) may or may not communicate a veto in a certain time frame. Positive feedback can be sent as well to shorten the response time for the access request. In case of approval and a signed contract, the user receives access to the data set that was applied for. This may include subsets of records according to data types that can be chosen and therefore a definition of a "minimum data unit" that can be managed. The user may need an easy-to-use, intuitive interface for querying data and tracking their applications, data that they have been granted access and expiration date, how to extend them etc.. Other users need the possibility to run more complex analyses on the data; some may even bring in their own data and /or own algorithm. This may require a more complex compute environment. Data may change over time because of new data points added (additional data types, additional time points) or data subjects' requests (deletion, rectification). In addition, data use may lead to enriched or

derived data also available through 1+MG. The users must be able to update datasets but also to request a stable version of the dataset that will be preserved in an unchanged form. For some use, archiving of the analysis and the possibility to re-run the analysis again up to 10 years later is required, in accordance with good scientific research and reproducibility practices. A data versioning (release) mechanism and tools are therefore needed. This should also include the possibility to identify when dataset versions can be deleted because there is no longer a need to retain them.

4. Introduction: Data Protection by Design and Default

Data protection by design and default (DPbDD) was introduced in the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and is anchored in Article 25. Organisational and technical safeguards have to be taken by the controller to implement the data protection principles for all processing of personal data.

It is important to notice that DPbDD is more than ensuring privacy, i.e. the protection of the individual against unauthorised disclosure of the data, DPbDD covers all data protection principles. These are described in Art. 5.1 GDPR:

- Transparency
- Lawfulness
- Fairness
- Purpose Limitation
- Data Minimisation
- Accuracy
- Storage limitation
- Integrity and confidentiality

DPbDD means that the compliance with these principles must be considered already when the processing is planned and not mapped afterwards (“by design”). The “by default” means that the default state of a system should be “closed” or “protected” and only those data necessary for the purpose should be processed.¹ Disclosure should be an active step that has to be planned in compliance with the above principles.

The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) has published the Guidelines 04/2019 (latest [version 2.0 from 20 October 2020](#)) on how to implement DPbDD.

It is the responsibility of the data controller to ensure the DPbDD. However, the data processor has the obligation to assist the data controller in the implementation of Articles 32 to 36 GDPR, which deal with the security of the processing and the data protection impact assessment. When the design of the processing and the IT systems are in compliance with the data protection principles, the demonstration of the sufficiency of the chosen organisational and technical safeguards is part of the accountability obligation of the data controller and a first step for the data protection impact assessment. Even where the providers of the IT infrastructure are only acting as data processors in the 1+MG initiative, they should provide expertise input in how the IT infrastructure should be designed with respect to technical and organisational measures (TOMs) to comply with the data protection principles, in particular

¹ See EDPB Guidelines 04/2019 subsection 2.2.1

on aspects of data integrity and confidentiality as well as to realise purpose limitation and data minimisation.

The so-called “Five Safes” developed in the UK in the context of access to statistical data is an approach that can be used to support the DPbDD exercise.² The Five Safes cover:³

- Safe projects : Is this use of the data appropriate, lawful, ethical and sensible?
- Safe people: Can the users be trusted to use it in an appropriate manner?
- Safe data: Does the data itself contain sufficient information to allow confidentiality to be breached?
- Safe settings: Does the access facility limit unauthorised use or mistakes?
- Safe outputs: Is the confidentiality maintained for the outputs of the management regime?

The “Five Safes” approach is increasingly used to design the solutions for data sharing by statistics offices. A general guidance on how the Five Safes can be used to create secure data environments for research was published recently by the UK Health Data Research Alliance: “Building Trusted Research Environments” (version [1.0 from 8 December 2021](#)).

This document provided an excellent starting point for the 1+MG DPbDD exercise. We subsequently adapted the "Five Safes" approach into a framework tailored to 1+MG, following envisaged data flows within the cross-border initiative, and taking into account distinct characteristics of the 1+MG forthcoming data governance. The analysis of the different stages will be organised according to the data protection principles of the GDPR, not the Five Safes to allow an easier demonstration of compliance, performance of a DPIA and auditing of 1+MG.

Please note that the current data governance for research use on which the DPbDD recommendations are based do not yet cover access by users outside the European Economic Area (EEA). In addition, the data governance for access in the context of rare diseases, which falls between research and healthcare, is also not yet decided.

5. DPbDD considerations for the IT infrastructure

“IT infrastructure” in the following covers all information and communication technology support of the operations of 1+MG. This goes beyond the management of data access and the provision of an analysis platform for data use and also includes information and workflow management of 1+MG. In this context, the data governance of 1+MG, implementing responsible and DPbDD driven procedures and the DPbDD-driven considerations on information management in 1+MG are relevant background documents. The current document recommends a list of requirements that the 1+MG IT infrastructure should fulfil. It is a first draft and may further develop based on the development of the data governance policy or use case requirements as pursued in the subsequent deployment projects such as the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project. It will have to be complemented with scientific requirements on the IT infrastructure (i.e. use case needs; interoperability requirements). 1+MG Working Groups for Interoperability and Secure IT environment (WG5) and ELSI (WG2) must work closely together to see how the requirements can be translated into workable solutions and define a roadmap for the implementation.

² For the background of the Five Safes, see: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Five_safes

³ <http://www.fivesafes.org/>

6. DPbDD requirements for the IT infrastructure in 1+MG along the data journey

Data inclusion

- Data transfer tools that are suitable for biomedical researchers and clinicians that allow secure transfers to the 1+MG IT infrastructure.
- Data integrity check after transfer has to be ensured (e.g. use of checksums, data scrubbing)
- Data format validation (e.g. for genomics data, associated metadata)
- Open to discussion: Secondary pseudonymisation of genome and phenotypic data separately and/or physical separation of genomic and phenotypic data on different servers
- Collection / uploading of structured metadata into suitable tools relevant for ingestion into the data management system (e.g. ELSI metadata relevant for data use) and for display in the data catalogue

Data hosting

- Storage that is secured against external and internal attacks and or accidental disclosure (e.g. no direct internet access);
- Protection against data loss (e.g. back-ups and disaster recovery)
- Open to discussion: Encryption of data where the IT environment allows fast decryption / encryption on the fly [criteria to consider: relevance / efficiency / cost as data are almost constantly in use]
- Access restriction to the data: default is no access, fine-grained access control lists (ACLs)
- Data management with possibility to send automated reminders in view of upcoming deadlines (end of access, end of retention time for a dataset version)
- Possibility for record-level metadata on version, use conditions, data use (see below) and retention time
- Ability to remove data from the active system (i.e. no longer accessible)
- Ability to restrict processing to certain users, purposes and subsets of data (at variable level, at data subject level) only (i.e. permit) from a certain time point onwards
- Ability to remove data from back-ups or restrict their restoring

Data discovery

- Central data catalogue that seamlessly comprises information from national data catalogues where applicable
- Data catalogue should offer sufficient characterisation of datasets for requesters to allow assessing the usability of the data for their purposes; ideally, also synthetic datasets are made available, also for purposes beyond data discovery but to test usefulness of the data. [Comment: synthetic data here would only be on the “lowest” requirement level - reflecting the structure of the data, not mimicking the content distribution and correlation]

- Option for data requesters to specify their type of access request (research, healthcare, policy development, other - still to be defined based on use case input)
-> such specification influences user/requester interface offered
- Possibility for requesters to select relevant data subjects based on genotype, phenotype and/or other features such as ethnic origin
- For subject level data discovery, the requester must also specify the area of research based on controlled vocabulary (e.g. disease specific, legal basis)
- Authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) that allows authentication of requesters by their employing institution and/or role (relevant roles are researcher, healthcare professional etc.).
- The AAI must be technically interoperable to allow for federated identity management.
- Data requesters must be able to log into one AAI implementation that gives access to data across all 1+MG sites.
- Possibility to block persons from access if they appear on a “blocked list”
- Offer suitable “terms of use” that need to be confirmed before the requester can start the search on a subject-level (i.e. data on individuals)
- Data management system that allows to limit data searches to relevant data only (tagging of data for use restrictions: offer only datasets for search that can be processed under a particular legal basis of the requester [if applicable], by the category of requester for the purposes of the project)
- Ensure that such focussed search cannot be bypassed and/or that incorrect behaviour is monitored / flagged (e.g. where the requester changes the purpose specification to change search)
- Data discovery tool that allows subject-level searches for genotype and/or phenotype without releasing information that can be used to readily identify subjects and/or reconstruct the data by single search or combination of multiple searches by built in protective features
- Logging of subject level searches
- Possibility to download / view synthetic datasets of relevant data collections

Access request: Support data governance procedures

- Data user portal that allows seamless transfer from data discovery to access request on the selected datasets, i.e. selection of data collections and/or a number of individual records on subject level data and launching the access request on that selection
- Web form for the collection of relevant information for access review and approval, depending on access request type. This includes the characterisation of access request based on controlled vocabulary matching the ELSI metadata (still to be defined) and the possibility to upload files such as ethics approvals or evaluation reports by funders.
- Possibility to launch the same access request by several institutions as joint controllers.
- Ideally: possibility for electronic signature for registered organisations’ signing officials.

- Ideally: possibility for users to be flagged as whitelisted, so that no separate confirmation to confirm the validity of the request is needed
- Possibility for documented approvals / rejections with justification and exchanges on request in the system.
- Access request management system that acquires the necessary access request information (from the user portal), notifications to the relevant actors, ideally validation of submissions by detecting obvious mistakes (e.g. missing elements; inconsistencies (where relevant)), allows communication between actors; API to retrieve information stored in the system.
- Archiving of access requests

Data use:

- Offering non-personal data to users for their purposes where reasonably possible (e.g. existing knowledge on variants; synthetic data)
- Possibility to issue, store and consume data permits; ideally also from different Data Providers for a joint analysis by the user
- Link approved access request to relevant data collection(s) or relevant data types and data subjects (individual records); includes handling of persistent identifiers for datasets
- Allow user operation in a virtual environment that allows operations over a distributed system or offer temporary data pooling as alternative
- Separating individual users accessing from the same user institution;
- Separating virtual workspaces allocated to the same user for different projects
- Strong (multi-factor) authentication ensuring verification of user identity, contribute link to EU eIdentities where these become available
- Only personal, no shared accounts
- Allow several users from the same controller (e.g. via user groups) as well as the possibility to include processors in the permit
- Possibility to give access only to the relevant records including only the data types needed of the relevant data subjects
- Ideally linking of genomic data and phenotypic data on the fly for data processing (from data on separate servers and/or different pseudonym), also decryption / encryption on the fly only when access is needed
- Possibility that external data, which is not held in 1+MG but parallel with the Data Provider or another Data Provider (e.g. public registry) can be linked to the respective records held internally for joint use.
- Possibility for collaborative approaches for data analysis where several users work on the same project
- Offer different user interfaces depending on the access request (healthcare professionals different to researcher; different rights / possibility to operate on the data)
- Open for decision: offer virtual desktop interface or “algorithm to the data” only

- Open for decision: allow 1+MG-held IT infrastructure only or include commercial cloud solutions
- Offer analysis environment for the deployment of containers for research analyses
- Only properly documented, versioned and secure software (e.g. through gitlab) can be offered for users; a comprehensive set of analysis tools / libraries has to be offered. Users should be allowed to run analyses from a list of approved workflows/pipelines. This should also include search and analysis tools with graphics / visualisation tools that are easy to use for users such as clinicians
- Where users bring in their own software, these need to be checked for malwares and, where applicable, security vulnerabilities. There should be functions and processes to validate the results if they stem from algorithms brought-in by the users.
- Establish a central container registry and the possibility to archive containers.
- Allow user management of access: suspend and resume work
- Possibility to archive and restore the project specific work environment during times of suspended activities
- Logging of data operations
- Monitoring for suspicious behaviour (e.g. certain access patterns; mismatch of stated datatypes / diseases of interest and data accessed)
- Airlocked system, only supervised methods for taking aggregated data / software / results out of the protected environment
- Possibility of data versioning in case of data deletion or rectification or updates with additional data points
- Possibility to archive processed datasets and allow referencing for publications
- Archiving of versioned datasets with information which projects rely on which version to allow reproducibility together with archived containers; a re-running of the analysis should work 10 years later still
- Information portal to provide information on all data use for general public in English, based on requester's information and publications based on data use as well as dedicated communication around data use; API to allow countries to display only projects relevant for the data collection in the country
- Common standards for the above requirements that allow deployment in a federated environment
- Where data use requires data pooling and/or transmission to a different compute environment, secure transfer mechanisms must be established; where data are temporarily stored in another IT infrastructure, safe delete must be ensured
- Automated search for publications based on mandatory reference to 1+MG
- Information management that allows messaging between users and Data Providers, e.g. for reporting incidental findings, requests for additional data / biosamples or recruitment of data subjects in new studies (including automatic management of "no contact" information)

General requirements

- A clear assignment of which considerations (requirements) should be covered during the software development phase and which are to be handled at deployment/operation phase (e.g. via SOPs).
- Implementation in certified compliance with ISO 27001 and ISO 27701.
- At minimum external audit, ideally certification (only certified data centres / compute environments are allowed to pool data across countries)
- Regular testing of effectiveness of safeguards
- Staff must be trained in data protection and IT security (focus depends on role)
- Staff must have secrecy clauses in their contracts where not already subject to professional secrecy by law.
- Data protection policy framework must be in place (minimum policies to be covered has to be agreed jointly)
- Joint agreement on requirements of what makes “secure systems”
- GDPR compliant log information management (how long are logs kept, how are they stored, who has access)
- Management of time-dependent processing (data, metadata, log data) including safe delete at the end of the retention time
- Contract management system with API to data information system
- Information management system that can link access requests to contracts to log files, users, containers, versioned dataset used etc. that is auditable

7. DPbDD considerations for the information management

Data protection compliant data management includes the management of relevant information on how data can be used but also requires the information on the actors along the data life cycle with their responsibilities and contacts, information on the data use itself, information about organisational and technical safeguards, including the management of such safeguards such as for pseudonymisation and secondary pseudonymisation. Accountability means that the measures taken must be auditable, which again sets up certain requirements for the documentation around the entire life cycle of data in the 1+MG.

The considerations on information management build on the mission of 1+MG, the data governance implementing DPbDD workflows, requirements of the GDPR and practical considerations that link the various needs. The definition of relevant structured and (where applicable) machine readable information is an important input for the design of the IT infrastructure. The current version is a first draft that will further develop with e.g. the decisions on the data governance. It should also be considered to be complemented by information requirements relevant from the user’s perspective. The 1+MG Working Groups for Standards (WG3), Interoperability and Secure IT environment (WG5) and ELSI (WG2) must work closely together to define how such information management can be implemented in 1+MG.

8. DPbDD driven information requirements in 1+MG along the data journey

Data inclusion

- Data provider who decides on inclusion and is responsible for specifying the use conditions
 - Legal entity
 - Scientific / clinical contact
 - Administrative contact
 - Legal representative contact
 - Data Protection Officer (DPO) contact
 - Information if Data Provider can be contacted for additional information
- Data use conditions metadata as derived from data subject consent and/or legal requirements [both collection-level and record-level information]
 - Categories of purposes for data use with respect to recipients
 - Limitations on territorial scope for users (only outside EEA can be limited)
 - Data subject's consent that Data Provider can disclose additional information where needed by data user
 - Information on data subjects where applicable, e.g. relevant vulnerabilities such as minors and anything that may have implications on processing
- Information around recontacting subjects [data subject-level information]
 - Purposes for re-contacting with communication channels (including [permanent] contacts) and language
 - Participation in research studies
 - Obtaining consent / active information on new purposes
 - General information provision
 - (Incidental findings)
 - General "no return" flag (initially collection level but will be specified on the level of data subjects)
- Information on data retention criteria / requirements / time
- Legal basis for inclusion
- Scientific metadata for all 1+MG data types as defined in 1+MG
- Metadata on changes in datasets (exercise of data subjects rights: deletion, rectification, changed use conditions; changes due to enrichment; changes due to additional data added etc.)
- Information on additional data beyond the 1+MG defined datasets or samples available at Data Provider [or potentially already stored in the 1+MG secure processing environment]
- Integrity check information (after data transfer and periodically during storage)
- Time stamp of upload

- Registration / versioning of datasets (creation of new dataset version 1.0 or adding to existing datasets creating new version 2.0)
- A universal unique identifier (UUID) of the same data and version (identical copy) assigned and used in all federated systems

Data hosting

- Information on data location of the different versions
- Information on retention for individual dataset versions as derived from inclusion data and use data
 - Data archived for project xy; duration of retention
 - Data under deletion request (to be deleted at the end of use or archiving; data not to be restored from backup)
- Information on changes of dataset on subject level
 - Versioning following update of data for new data points
 - Versioning of datasets for changes (rectified)
 - Dataset current version “no more use for N / at all” (objection, withdrawal of consent, delete request)
- Pseudonym matching table (if applicable)
- Controller for hosting
- Legal basis for hosting (if not defined by 1+MG)
- Encryption keys

Access request:

- Type of access request
- Information provided by requester
 - For research project
 - For healthcare use
 - For policy development
- Log information of subject-level searches by requester
- Information on (institutionally) whitelisted and blocked researchers
- Information on signing officials for each institution
- Association of records with defined access requests, i.e. the possibility to keep an auditable track of which records are / were used for which access and the easy information, e.g. where a data subject asks in which projects their data was used.
- Suggested decision by central DAC, where applicable: feedback of National Coordination Points, final decision on request as suggested in the data governance policy (per collection / subset if necessary)
- Objections by individual data subjects
- Logging all interactions until approval and access provision (who, when, what)
- (Contract)

Data use:

- Store permits / contract including expiry dates
- Information on data use
 - For projects / use application: uses version xy of dataset
 - For Data: booked or used for project / use application xy (on record level)
- Documentation on any changes to permit with time-stamped versioning
 - Regarding datasets
 - Regarding controllers and personnel with access
 - Regarding duration
- Research results
 - Information on publication linked to use request (and due to that, data subject)
 - Information on communication on publication (where applicable)
 - Information on patents / products / services derived from use request
- Healthcare results [still subject to healthcare reuse data governance]
 - Feedback on outcome
- Policy development results [still subject to policy development data governance]
 - Outcome report (if or if not intended outcome was achieved)
 - Link to established policies (where applicable)
- “No return” flag for incidental findings
- Log information for data use
- Documentation of exports
- Archiving requirements
- Data stability requirements by data user, i.e. the user is able to indicate at a certain time point when it should not be possible to delete any records from the dataset used in his analysis; may refer to dataset still in use for analysis or for a dataset to be frozen for archiving; needs to be complemented with a written justification
- Versions of datasets
- Reference numbers of workflows in a workflow registry where detailed information on software, data used and IT systems are stored
- Information on any data transmissions (where, when, why)

General

- Information on audits / extension of certification
- Documentation of the testing of the efficiency of safeguards
- Documentation of system changes / upgrades / incidents
- Documentation of data breaches
- Documentation of data and metadata definitions

- Recording of decisions on the different levels
- Documentation of DPIAs
- Documentation of exchanges with DPO and CISO
- Documentation of trainings
- Documentation policy framework with versioning

Information to be provided in research access request [minimum]

- Project title
- Name and contact details of the Principal investigator of the project
- Information about the institution
(Institution needs to be registered including information on signing official and DPO; where several signing officials are applicable, the relevant official is to be chosen)
- Persons who will have access to the data (PI and his/her group)
- Scientific abstract
- Lay summary of project that can be provided to the data subjects whose data are used
- Data analysis plan that describes the data types and analysis approaches to be employed to achieve the goal of the project
- Description of any machine learning algorithms / AI employed, developed, trained, validated, or exported by the project.
- Information on enriched data (e.g. annotations) and derived data (e.g. curated data) that may be generated through the project
- Estimated project duration
- Legal basis under Art. 6.1 GDPR and legitimation under Art. 9.2
- Funding source(s)
- Peer-review of project where applicable
- Research ethics application and decision for the specific project
- Machine readable characterisation of project based on controlled vocabulary (e.g. field of research, commercial versus pre-competitive research, data types to be accessed, etc.), (checked for consistency with analysis plan and other project documents by 1+MG Access Office).
Justification: this will be necessary for using automated tools to check that access requests are consistent with data availability conditions
- Selected data or types of data to be accessed (should be automatically selected from the catalogue browsing and/or Beacon search)
- Information if access request is only upheld if ALL selected records are available (or potentially what a critical % of available records is)
- Status of researcher as white-listed / black-listed or confirmation of validity of request by a signing official at the requester's institution
- Information on required processing environment (required to assess the feasibility of conducting the research in the 1+MG environment, the risk of processing, compile processing agreement and provide a quote on compute costs where applicable)

- Software needed; if applicable: own software to be introduced
- Information on own data that may be uploaded for the research [data types, volume, data origin]